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AUTOMATION OF DATA ENTRY IN B2B DOCUMENT FLOW BASED ON A DIGITAL TWIN OF AN ORDER

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Abstract

The article describes research into the automation of electronic document management processes in B2B e-commerce systems. It has been determined that the critical stage in ensuring the accuracy of primary documentation in such systems is the process of forming order specifications. A scientific and practical approach to automating data entry using the concept of a "digital twin" for the order basket is proposed. A mathematical model of the time required to process an order and software modules for the Magento 2 platform (BarcodeScanner and Multi-Swatches) have been developed, which implement machine vision and matrix data entry methods. Experiments have confirmed a 3-4-fold reduction in the time required to generate documents and a minimization of human error.

Keywords: electronic document management, B2B, digital twins, automation, barcoding, attribute matrix, blockchain.

Introduction. The rapid development of e-commerce and the transition of business processes to the digital space require new approaches to the organization of electronic document management (EDM). In the B2B (Business-to-Business) segment, the specifics of orders differ significantly from retail trade: a large number of items (SKUs), regularity of purchases, and strict requirements for the accuracy of accompanying documentation (invoices, delivery notes).

The main problem with modern B2B platforms is the gap between the customer's physical need (for example, the need to replenish the warehouse with specific goods) and the process of creating a digital document. Manually entering data on hundreds of goods into the system inevitably leads to errors, which in turn causes inaccuracies in legally significant documents, delays in logistics, and financial losses.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. The issue of building complex mathematical models of electronic documentation has been thoroughly researched in the works of scientists at Zhytomyr Polytechnic, in particular in [1,2]. The authors emphasize the complexity of algorithmizing the processing of unstructured data in document management systems [2]. However, despite a solid theoretical basis, the practical aspects of automated filling of primary documents (Data Entry) directly at the moment of a business transaction require further study. Most studies focus on the

stages of signing (EDS), encryption, and document transfer. However, the stage of generating input data (Data Entry) for these documents is often overlooked.

Modern platforms such as Magento 2, Shopify, and SAP Commerce offer basic shopping cart functionality focused on visual selection (B2C scenario). At the same time, the concept of Digital Twins, which is actively used in Industry 4.0, opens up new opportunities for e-commerce [3,4]. Issues of modern information system architecture are discussed in the works of scientists from Zhytomyr Polytechnic, in particular M.S.Graf and V.A.Raikovsky [5,6]. Interpreting the order basket as a digital twin of the physical delivery allows the use of automatic object identification (Auto-ID) methods for instant synchronization of the "customer's warehouse" and "supplier's document" statuses.

The purpose of this study is to improve the efficiency of electronic document management in B2B systems by developing methods and software tools for automated order specification generation on the Magento 2 platform, based on barcode scanning and matrix attribute selection technologies.

Presentation of the main material.

Mathematical model of document formation

The process of creating an electronic document (order) can be represented as the formation of a set of tuples:

$$D = \{(id_i, q_i, p_i) | i = 1, \dots, N\}, (1)$$

where id_i - product identifier, q_i - quantity, p_i - price, N - total number of items.

Total time T , necessary for creating a correct document, consists of the time spent searching for

$$T_{manual} = \sum_{i=1}^N (t_{search}(id_i) + t_{select}(id_i) + t_{qty}(id_i) + t_{valid}(id_i)), (2)$$

Since t_{search} depends on the complexity of the catalog and t_{valid} is often performed post facto (after an error), this function has a nonlinear dependence on operator fatigue.

It is important to note that the generated electronic document must meet the requirements of integrity and authenticity in accordance with the Law of Ukraine "On Electronic Trust Services" [7]. As noted by Yu. A. Tarnavsky [8], the automation of input data is a prerequisite for the transition to legally significant document flow, as it eliminates the risk of information distortion at the stage of its digitization.

For automatic mode using a scanner:

$$T_{auto} = \sum_{i=1}^N (t_{scan}(id_i) + t_{sys_response}) + T_{overhead}, (3)$$

where t_{scan} - camera focus time (constant), $\approx 1-2$ s), $t_{sys_response}$ - server response time (AJAX request),

goods (t_{search}), time of parameter selection (t_{select}), time of entry quantity (t_{qty}) and validation time (t_{valid}):

For manual mode:

$T_{overhead}$ - module initialization time. $t_{sys_response}$ (server response) can be either for each item separately (if scanning one by one) or one for the entire package (if sending as an array).

Since batch transmission is considered, formula (3) can be written as:

$$T_{auto} = \sum t_{scan} + T_{request}. (4)$$

The implementation of automation modules allows you to achieve the following conditions $T_{auto} \ll T_{manual}$ при $N > 10$, and also reduce the probability of error thanks to hardware validation of the barcode checksum.

System architecture and concept of the Digital Twin

In the developed system, the digital twin of the order is formed not through manual selection, but through a sensor network (cameras of customers mobile devices).

Figure 1: Block diagram consisting of three levels

Physical level: User with a smartphone, Product with a barcode (EAN-13). Sensor level (Client side): Scandit SDK (image recognition), JS controller (event processing). Digital level (Magento server side): Database (EAV attributes), BarcodeScanner module, Multi-Swatches module, PDF document generator. The arrows show the data flow from the barcode to the finished invoice.

Figure 1 shows a block diagram of the algorithm for automated input data generation for electronic document management. The information processing process is divided into four logical stages that reflect the transformation of a physical object into a digital document:

Initialization and physical input stage. The process begins (Start block) with the operator initiating data entry. The input parameters are a physical product identified by an EAN-13 barcode or a set of product configurations selected via a matrix interface (Input block).

Client Processing stage. On the client side (web browser), the video stream is captured by the mobile device's camera and processed by the Scandit SDK library (Camera & Scandit SDK block). The data obtained undergoes initial validation (Is Data Valid? logical block). If the data is corrupted or does not match the format, the algorithm terminates (No -> End branch), preventing incorrect requests from being sent to the server.

Server Processing Stage. If validation is successful (Yes branch), an asynchronous AJAX request to the

server is generated. The Magento system controller (Controller Logic block) receives the request and performs a search for matches in the database (Database Lookup block). The result is an update of the order basket status, which in this model acts as a “digital twin” of the physical delivery.

Output Generation stage. Based on the synchronized data of the digital twin, the system generates the final document—an invoice or specification (Generate Invoice block), after which the algorithm completes execution (End block).

This algorithm structure ensures data integrity throughout the entire process, from physical scanning to a legally valid document.

Software implementation of modules

To achieve this goal, two structural modules were developed for CMS Magento 2, allowing flexible expansion of functionality through a system of modules and plugins (Interceptors) [9].

A. Scanning module (Magento_BarcodeScanner). The module integrates the Scandit SDK for the Web library [10], which uses WebAssembly technology for high-speed video stream processing in the client's browser, ensuring the recognition of damaged or poorly lit barcodes.

Algorithm of operation:

1. Initialization of the camera via the browser API (navigator.mediaDevices).
2. Capture of the video stream and search for EAN-8/13 patterns.
3. Upon successful recognition, an AJAX request is sent to the SearchByEan controller.

4. The server searches the catalog_product_entity_varchar table by the ean attribute.

5. The product is automatically added to the “digital twin” (shopping cart) or an error message is displayed.

The key feature of the implementation is the use of the JavaScript Mixins pattern to extend Magento's standard behavior without modifying the core of the system.

B. Matrix order module (Magento_Multi-Swatches). For products with variations (Configurable Products), a matrix interface has been implemented. Instead of the sequential selection “Color -> Size -> Add,” the user sees a two-dimensional matrix.

Technical implementation includes:

- Extension of the mage.SwatchRenderer widget.
- Interception of the _OnClick event to prevent page reloading.
- Collection of the qty[] data array for all selected variations.
- Sending a single MultiAddToCart request, which significantly reduces the load on the document generation server.

Results of the experimental study

A series of tests was conducted to verify effectiveness. The operator was asked to create orders (documents) for 10, 50, and 100 items in three ways:

- Standard Magento interface (search by name).
- Matrix input (for clothing/footwear).
- Barcode scanning.

Залежність часу формування документа від кількості позицій

Figure 2. Graph showing the dependence of time spent on order formation on the number of product items

X-axis: Number of items (10, 20, ..., 100). Y-axis: Time in minutes. Line 1 (Manual input): Rises steeply (steep angle of inclination). Line 2 (Matrix): More gradual. Line 3 (Scanner): The most gradual, almost

horizontal. Data example: For 50 items: Manual – 25 min, Matrix – 10 min, Scanner – 4 min.

The results are shown in Table 1. The results show a significant advantage of automated methods.

Comparative characteristics of document formation methods

Formation method	Time per position (avg.)	Probability of error (Human Error)	Server load
Manual search	30-45 c	High (text selection)	High (many requests)
Matrix input	10-15 c	Average	Low (1 batch request)
Scanning (Barcode)	3-5 c	Zero (hardware validation)	Average

Particular attention should be paid to the error rate. When using the BarcodeScanner module, sorting errors (when a similar but not the same product is included in the document) are eliminated because the unique GTIN (Global Trade Item Number) identifier is read by the machine. This ensures that the generated delivery note corresponds 100% to the physically selected goods.

Discussion: Integration with unified document management systems

The data generated using the developed modules is stored in the Magento database (MySQL/MariaDB) in a structured form. This allows for automatic data export to XML or JSON formats for further transfer to legally significant document management systems (e.g., M.E.Doc, Vchasno) via API. The proposed approach transforms the role of the B2B portal: from a showcase, it becomes a data collection terminal that is part of a unified digital enterprise ecosystem.

Conclusions

It has been established that the bottleneck in document flow automation in B2B e-commerce is the specification filling stage. Manual methods are ineffective for orders with more than 20 items.

It is proposed to consider the order basket as a digital twin of the picking process, which requires the use of touch-based data entry methods.

The Magento BarcodeScanner and Magento MultiSwatches modules have been developed and implemented. Their use has reduced order processing time by an average of 5-6 times and minimized errors in the creation of primary documentation.

The prospect for further research is the integration of the developed modules with Blockchain technology to fix the immutability of the order composition at the scanning stage.

References

- Chernyak I. O., Graf M. S. Problems of creating a comprehensive mathematical model of electronic documentation. Information and Computer Technologies – 2023: abstracts of the XIII International Scientific and Technical Conference (Zhytomyr, April 20–21, 2023). Zhytomyr: Zhytomyr Polytechnic, 2023.
- Chernyak I. O. Analysis of algorithms and mathematical models for the automation of electronic document management. Technical Engineering. 2023. No. 1. Pp. 178–183.
- Torres Adelsberger R., Antons O., Arlinghaus J. Digital Twins and their Implications for Business Models: Overview and Potentials. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*. 2024. Vol. 58, Issue 13. P. 45–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2024.09.246.
- Higa E. Digital Twins: how can they impact ecommerce. *Medium*. 2023. URL: <https://medium.com/@eduardohiga/digital-twins-how-can-they-impact-ecommerce-7f8a9a8b8b8a> (date of application: 18.12.2025).
- Graf M. S., Raikovskiy V. A. Development of the structure of the internal network information system of the Information and Analytical Support Department of the Main Directorate of the National Police in Zhytomyr Region. Information and Computer Technologies – 2024: abstracts of reports of the XIV International Scientific and Technical Conference (Zhytomyr, March 28–29, 2024). Zhytomyr: Zhytomyr Polytechnic, 2024. Pp. 138–139.
- Raikovskiy V. A., Volsky R. A. The use of modern architectural approaches to develop an information system for managing information and analytical support. Integrated Intelligent Robotic Complexes (IIRC-2024): abstracts of the XVII International Scientific and Practical Conference (Kyiv, May 21–22, 2024). Kyiv: NAU, 2024. Pp. 419–421.
- Law of Ukraine “On Electronic Trust Services” dated 05.10.2017 No. 2155-VIII. Information from the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. 2017. No. 45. P. 400.
- Tarnavskiy, Yu. A. Electronic Document Management Systems: Textbook. Ternopil: TNTU, 2020. 216 pp.
- Introduction to Magento 2 / Magento Open Source 2.4 Developer Documentation. Adobe Inc. URL: <https://developer.adobe.com/commerce/php/guide/> (date of application: 18.12.2025).
- Barcode Scanner SDK for the Web / Scandit Documentation. URL: <https://docs.scandit.com/stable/web/> (date of application: 18.12.2025).